

Study on effect of air gap thickness in Otto configuration based SPR chips

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Abstract—In this study, Otto configuration based SPR chip with multiple air-gaps is designed. SPR characteristics of the proposed SPR chip are analyzed using FEM simulation. The proposed SPR chip has four sections which have separate air-gaps of 0.9 μm , 1.2 μm , 1.5 μm and 1.8 μm , sequentially. Each section of the SPR chip has different SPR characteristics according to the air-gap thickness. Optimized SPR effect is occurred when a laser beam which has a wavelength of 785 nm and 977 nm is reflected at the section 2 and section 3, respectively.

Keywords—SPR, Otto configuration, FEM simulation, DRIE

I. INTRODUCTION

Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) means that the resonant oscillation of conduction electrons at the interface between metal and dielectric material caused by incident light. A number of sensors based on the SPR effect, which have advantages of needlessness of indicator and real-time measurement, have been used in various applications such as chemical and biosensors [1-2]. Most of SPR sensors using several-hundred nanometer thick film of metal layer are based on the Kretschmann configuration or Otto configuration. Generally, because of a convenience of fabrication process, commercialized SPR sensor systems are based on the Kretschmann configuration. However, the use of adhesion layer in the Kretschmann configuration cause a negative effect on the SPR characteristics [3]. In the Otto configuration, the metal film is separated from the glass substrate and consequently, SPR characteristics can be improved due to absence of adhesion layer as analyzed in the previous study [3].

Recently, the concept of Otto configuration based SPR sensors have been increasingly exploited for development of optical sensors [4, 5]. In the Otto configuration based SPR sensors, optimized wavelength of the incident light is proportional to air-gap thickness between a glass substrate and top of metal film.

In this study, an Otto configuration based SPR chip with multiple air-gaps is proposed and designed with mathematical calculation. Effect on air-gap thickness in Otto configuration based SPR chip is analyzed by using FEM simulation.

II. DESIGN

A. Otto configuration based SPR chip with multiple air-gaps

A schematic view of the proposed Otto configuration based SPR chip is shown in Fig. 1. The whole size of the proposed SPR chip is $114 \times 114 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$. The proposed SPR chip consists of a glass substrate and a silicon substrate and it has four sections which have separate air-gap thicknesses of 0.9 μm , 1.2 μm , 1.5 μm and 1.8 μm , respectively, as shown in Fig. 2. A 300 nm-thick gold film is used as a metal film. A diameter of inlet and outlet are designed to be 1.8 mm for the gas detection or biosensing experiment which will be conducted as a further study. Fig. 3 shows mathematically calculated minimum reflectance when the wavelength of the incident laser is varied from 500 nm to 1200 nm. The minimum reflectance means that the incident light is absorbed by surface plasmons on the metal film. Therefore, the lowest minimum reflectance can be understood as a best condition for optimized SPR characteristics. In this result, we expected that the proposed SPR chip can be used for efficient SPR sensing when a laser beam which has a wavelength of 785 nm or 977 nm is reflected at the section 2 and section 3, respectively.

Fig. 1. A schematic view of the proposed SPR chip

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Fig. 2. A cross-section view of the proposed SPR chip.

III. FEM SIMULATION

Fig. 4 shows the simulated SPR curve using FEM simulation (COMSOL Multiphysics®) based on the design parameters with TM polarized laser which has a wavelength of 785 nm and 977 nm. An incident angle of the laser is swept from 38° to 48° . In this simulation result, reflectance values at the resonance angle are simulated to be 0.004 at 42.022° , 0.135 at 42.074° , 0.153 at 41.915° and 0.002 at 42.022° , respectively, according to the section 2 and section 3 with different air-gaps. From this simulation results it is verified that the proposed SPR chip can be used with the laser sources with 785 nm and 977 nm wavelength for the sensitive chemical sensing system.

Fig. 3. Mathematically calculated SPR effect with different air-gap thickness.

Fig. 4. FEM simulation results based on the proposed SPR chip

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, the effect of the air-gap thickness in Otto configuration based SPR chips is studied using FEM simulation. The FEM simulation results of the SPR effect with parameters of the proposed SPR chip agree well with the mathematically calculated results. We expected that the results of the study will be effectively used for design of the Otto configuration based SPR sensor systems.

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